

Partial molar volumes, viscosity *B*-coefficient and hydration number of some pharmacologically important drugs in aqueous solutions

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Partial molar volumes (ϕ_v^0) at infinite dilution and viscosity *B*-coefficient of three drugs like pseudoephedrine hydrochloride (PSE), phenylephrine hydrochloride (PHE) and salbutamol sulfate (SBS) have been determined at 25, 30, 37 and 40° in aqueous medium. The observed ϕ_v^0 and *B*-coefficient values show greater than the corresponding values for inorganic ions; these values are in line with similar structured drug molecules.

The ϕ_v^0 values vary with temperature as a power series ($\phi_v^0 = A + BT + CT^2$) of temperature. The structure-making or -breaking capacity of the electrolytic drug has been inferred from the values of hydration number (n_H) and sign of $(\delta^2\phi_v^0/\delta T^2)_p$, which follows the order, PHE < PSE < SBS. All the studied drugs behave as structure-breaker in the present system.

Drug-macromolecular interaction is an important phenomenon in physiological media¹. Thermodynamic properties like partial molar volumes and viscosity *B*-coefficient are convenient parameters in interpreting molecular interactions in solution phase². It is to be noted that drug action can be achieved with a small amount of drugs as high concentrations are rarely achieved *in vivo*, therefore, ion-solvent interactions are the controlling forces in dilute solution.

We have undertaken a study of physical properties of several drug molecules, many of which are CNS-active. *Matubayasi and Ueda*³ proposed that the volume of anaesthetic molecules in the membranes is of prime importance for the mechanism of anesthesia, and it occurs when the volume of anesthetic molecule reaches a critical value in the cell membrane. The present paper reports our finding on three drugs : (i) pseudoephedrine hydrochloride (PSE), which is stereoisomer of ephedrine and has similar sympathomimatic action, (ii) phenylephrine hydrochloride (PHE), which is a sympathomimatic agent, which has predominately alpha-adrenergic activity and is without stimulating effects on central nervous system and (iii) salbutamol sulfate (SBS), which is a direct acting sympathomimatic agent with predominantly beta-adrenergic activity.

Evaluation of reliable partial molar expansibility $(\delta\phi_v^0/\delta T)_p$ needs ϕ_v^0 values at various temperatures⁴, sign of second derivatives of partial molar expansibility gives information regarding structure-making or -breaking tendency of molecules⁵.

Results and Discussion

Apparent molar volumes of PSE, PHE and SBS have been calculated from density measurements, at 25, 30, 37 and 40° using eqn. (1),

$$\phi_v = \frac{1000(d_0 - d)}{Cd_0} + \frac{M}{d_0} \quad (1)$$

where, d_0 and d are densities of water and drug solutions respectively, M is the molecular weight of drugs and C the concentration (mol dm⁻³). The plots of ϕ_v against square-root of molar concentration were found to be linear with positive slope. The limiting apparent molar volumes (ϕ_v^0) have been calculated using the least-square fit to the plots of ϕ_v vs $C^{1/2}$ using Masson equation⁶,

$$\phi_v = \phi_v^0 + S_v C^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

The values of ϕ_v^0 and S_v are recorded in Table 1. The ϕ_v^0 values obtained by the use of eqn. (2) are significantly larger in magnitude relative to ϕ_v^0 of simple inorganic ions⁷. There are scanty reports on the ϕ_v^0 of drugs molecules. Our values, however, are in line with that of Iqbal and Verrall¹ for drugs with similar structures. The ϕ_v^0 follows the order, PHE < PSE < SBS. First two drugs are taken as their chlorides and the third is taken as its sulfate. They would, therefore, behave as electrolyte in water. PSE and PHE are

present as univalent and SBS is as a divalent cation. The size and shape factors are more favorable for SBS, which shows a large values of ϕ_v^0 . The temperature dependence of ϕ_v^0 of PSE, PHE and SBS has been expressed by eqns. (3–5), respectively,

$$\phi_v^0 = 1.6583 \times 10^{-4} - 1.2814 \times 10^{-7} T + 2.7487 \times 10^{-9} T^2 \quad (3)$$

$$\phi_v^0 = 1.5082 \times 10^{-4} - 2.4853 \times 10^{-8} T + 1.1742 \times 10^{-9} T^2 \quad (4)$$

$$\phi_v^0 = 4.2934 \times 10^{-4} - 3.6617 \times 10^{-7} T + 8.4305 \times 10^{-9} T^2 \quad (5)$$

The apparent molar expansibility, $\phi_E^0 = (\delta\phi_v^0/\delta T)_p$ calculated from eqns. (3–5) has been found to increase with temperature (Table 3), suggesting caging effect⁸.

The structure-making or -breaking capacity of drugs PSE, PHE and SBS could be explained from the sign of $(\delta^2\phi_v^0/\delta T^2)_p$. Accordingly, positive sign⁹ of $(\delta^2\phi_v^0/\delta T^2)_p$ suggests the structure-maker and negative sign suggests the structure-breaker solute. For studied drugs all values of $(\delta^2\phi_v^0/\delta T^2)_p$ of are positive, therefore, PHE, PSE and SBS are structure-maker and follows the order : PHE < PSE < SBS. Viscosity *B*-coefficients was derived from Jones-Dole equation¹⁰ for dilute solution (*C* < 0.10 *M*) using eqn. (6),

$$\eta_r = 1 + AC^{1/2} + BC \quad (6)$$

The plots of $[(\eta_r - 1)/C^{1/2}]$ vs $C^{1/2}$ were found to be linear for PSE, PHE and SBS in water for all temperatures. The slope of plot yields viscosity *B*-coefficients and the values are presented in Table 1. Viscosity *B*-coefficients originally introduced as an empirical form has been found to depend upon solute-solvent interactions and on the relative size, shape of solute and solvent molecules.

Viscosity *B*-coefficients values for PSE, PHE and SBS are positive and larger than the values of simple inorganic ions¹¹, though the similar high values are reported for carbohydrate and other organic compounds, which may be due to the size effect. Larger viscosity *B*-coefficient values indicate structure-making capacity of the drug molecules. The viscosity *B*-coefficient values slightly decrease with temperatures¹². The order of viscosity *B*-coefficient is PHE < PSE < SBS. In this case, *B*-coefficient values of SBS is much larger than PSE and PHE. The same trends are shown in ϕ_v^0 and ϕ_E^0 . The effect of solute on the *B*-coefficient of particles arises from the fact that they lie across the fluid stream lines and are subjected to tortional forces¹³. Viscosity *B*-coefficient are related to effective volume (V_h) by

equation, $B = a V_h \times 10^{-3}$ for unsolvated species of roughly spherical molecules in normal solvent; *a* should lie between 0 and 2.5, hence $0 < B/\phi_v^0 < 2.5$, ϕ_v^0 values will however, be lower than that expected for an unsolvated solute because of electrostriction and B/ϕ_v^0 values must be larger and ϕ_v^0 is smaller. The order of B/ϕ_v^0 are PHE < PSE < SBS at all temperatures (Table 2). Values of B/ϕ_v^0 of PHE is less than 2.5. PSE and SBS are greater than 2.5. The B/ϕ_v^0 values for SBS are greater than 2.5, showing a distinct hydration in this case. For all three drugs, B/ϕ_v^0 values decrease with temperature. At higher temperatures water monomers have higher vibrational energy, which may be responsible for less hydration. The hydration number of PSE, PHE and SBS was calculated using eqn. (7),

Table 1. Partial molar volume (ϕ_v^0), experimental slope (S_v) and viscosity *B*-coefficient of PSE, PHE and SBS in water at different temperatures

Temp. °C	$\phi_v^0 \times 10^6$ m ³ mol ⁻¹	$S_v \times 10^6$ m ³ kg ^{1/2} mol ^{-3/2}	<i>B</i> dm ³ mol ⁻¹
PSE			
25	164.36	6.38	0.510
30	164.43	7.28	0.490
37	164.90	6.84	0.473
40	165.08	6.84	0.466
PHE			
25	150.93	5.60	0.328
30	151.15	5.71	0.324
37	151.49	5.46	0.320
40	151.72	5.29	0.317
SBS			
25	425.42	12.00	1.647
30	426.03	12.10	1.625
37	427.21	10.92	1.600
40	428.25	9.81	1.570

$$n_H = \frac{0.4 B - V_{ion}}{\phi_v^0} \quad (7)$$

where, *B*, V_{ion} and ϕ_v^0 are viscosity *B*-coefficient, molar volume of bare ion and partial molar volume of solute molecule, respectively. Molar volume of bare ion was calculated using eqn. (8),

$$V_{ion} = 4/3 \pi r^3 \lambda_A \quad (8)$$

Table 2. Hydration number (n_H) and B/ϕ_v^0 of PSE, PHE and SBS in water at different temperatures

Temp. °C	PSE		PHE		SBS	
	n_H	B/ϕ_v^0	n_H	B/ϕ_v^0	n_H	B/ϕ_v^0
25	1.240	3.103	0.867	2.173	1.548	3.871
30	1.191	2.980	0.856	2.144	1.525	3.814
37	1.146	2.868	0.843	2.112	1.497	3.745
40	1.128	2.823	0.834	2.089	1.466	3.666

The values of r were calculated from the knowledge of maximum end-to-end distance in three-dimensional projection of drug molecule through computer simulation. The values of r thus obtained for PSE (4.17 Å), PHE (4.81 Å) and SBS (4.80 Å), corresponding V_{ion} are (182.94, 280.75, 279.10) $\times 10^{-6}$ (cm³ mol⁻¹). The values of calculated hydration number (n_H) are presented in Table 3. Hydration number follow the order : PHE < PSE < SBS. Higher values can examine the effect of CH₂OH and OH on the *meta* and *para* positions of SBS ring. These groups are may be responsible for high values of n_H .

Table 3. Limiting apparent molar expansibility (ϕ_E^0) for PSE, PHE and SBS in water at different temperatures

Temp. °C	$\phi_E^0 \times 10^4$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)		
	PSE	PHE	SBS
25	0.929	3.386	5.535
30	3.678	4.560	13.966
37	7.526	6.204	24.769
40	9.175	6.908	30.827

Experimental

The drugs PSE, PHE and SBS (pharmacopial grade)¹⁴ were used as such. Double-distilled water used throughout having conductance less than 1×10^{-6} mhos. The first two drugs were taken as their chloride and SBS as its sulfate.

A Mettler balance was used for weighing, within ± 0.01 mg, the necessary buoyancy correction was applied. The density of water and drug solutions were determined in a 10 ml bicapillary pycnometers. The observed density of double distilled water was 997.04 kg m⁻³ at 25°, which is close to literature⁷. Density values were reproducible within ± 0.02 kg m⁻³.

Viscosity was measured by using Schott Gerate AVS 350 (Germany) measuring system, equipped with a Ubbelohde viscometer. In all the measurements kinetic energy correction was taken into account, using methods suggested

by Hagenbach (AVS 350 viscosity measuring system, Instruction Manual, Schott Gerate Hofheim, IS Germany 1983). Experiments were performed on at least five replicates for each solution at each temperature and the results averaged. The reproducibility in the viscosity measurement was $\pm 0.02\%$.

For all the measurements temperature were maintained within $\pm 0.02^\circ$.

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